

Comparative Study between Early and Delayed Ileostomy ClosureVipin Yadav¹, Neel Kamal Gupta², Akhilesh Gopalsingh Sukhlecha³, Bharat Bhushan Patidar⁴, Ridham Trivedi⁵, Jayesh Ghai⁶, Jatin Lakhani⁷, Devashish Verma⁸¹PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur²Professor and Unit Head, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur³Professor, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur⁴3rd Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur⁵2nd Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur⁶2nd Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur⁷1st Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur⁸1st Year PG Resident, Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Sitapura, Jaipur

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Abstract:**Background:** Ileostomy is a common surgical procedure performed as either a protective or emergency measure in various clinical scenarios. While ileostomy closure is typically performed three to six months after the initial surgery, the timing of this procedure remains a subject of debate. The distinction between early and delayed ileostomy closure is critical as it can significantly impact patient outcomes, including morbidity, mortality, and quality of life.**Objectives:** This study aims to compare the morbidity and mortality associated with early (4-6 weeks) versus delayed (8-12 weeks) ileostomy closure. Specifically, it seeks to evaluate post-stoma closure complications, the indications for stoma formation, complications related to the stoma, intraoperative parameters, and the duration of hospital stay between the two groups.**Methodology:** This prospective observational study was conducted from September 2022 to March 2024 at the Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur. A total of 60 patients who underwent ileostomy closure were included and divided into two groups: early closure (4-6 weeks post-surgery) and delayed closure (8-12 weeks post-surgery). Patients were selected based on specific inclusion criteria, including age, gender, and the absence of postoperative complications prior to closure. Data were collected on intraoperative parameters such as operative time and adhesion formation, as well as postoperative outcomes including hospital stay duration and stoma-related complications. Statistical analysis was performed to compare outcomes between the two groups, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.**Results:** The study analyzed 60 patients who underwent ileostomy closure, divided into two groups: early closure (30 patients) and delayed closure (30 patients). The mean hospital stay was slightly shorter in the early closure group (6.98±2.71 days) compared to the delayed closure group (7.25±2.62 days), although this difference was not statistically significant. Intraoperative adhesion was found to be significantly higher in the delayed closure group (36.7%) compared to the early closure group (10.0%), with a p-value of 0.015. Post-stoma closure complications were also more common in the early closure group, particularly wound infections, which were the most frequent complication. There was no mortality reported in the early closure group, whereas one death was recorded in the delayed closure group.**Conclusion:** Early ileostomy closure appears to be a feasible and effective alternative to the conventional delayed approach, with the potential to reduce stoma-related morbidity and enhance the quality of life for patients. However, careful patient selection is crucial to minimize the risks of complications, particularly wound infections. Further research is recommended to refine patient selection criteria and optimize the timing of ileostomy closure.**Keywords:** Early, Delayed, Ileostomy.

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Introduction

The creation of an ileostomy is a critical procedure often performed in emergency abdominal settings where primary repair of the colon is at high risk of failure. This situation is particularly common in cases involving gross peritoneal contamination or severe inflammation of the colon, which can arise in patients with conditions such as hemodynamic instability, enteric perforations, or tuberculosis. [1] Despite advancements in surgical techniques, the formation of an ileostomy remains a challenging decision, both for patients and medical professionals, due to its significant impact on the patient's quality of life. In developed countries, ileostomy is typically performed as a protective measure for distal colorectal or ileoanal pouch anastomosis, helping to prevent complications from anastomotic leakage.² However, in developing countries like India, where patients often present late in the course of their illness, ileostomies are more commonly performed in emergency settings. Infectious conditions such as enteric or tubercular perforations frequently necessitate the procedure, and the late presentation of these patients often precludes primary closure. [2] This disparity in patient profiles between developed and developing nations underscores the need for context-specific research on ileostomy management.

One of the most significant challenges in managing patients with an ileostomy is determining the optimal timing for its closure. For patients with resectable primary rectal cancer, low anterior resection (LAR) combined with total mesorectal excision is considered the best surgical approach. [3,4] However, anastomotic leakage (AL) remains the most feared complication following LAR, with a prevalence ranging from 3 to 25%. [5,6] To mitigate this risk, a loop ileostomy is often constructed to divert the flow of intestinal contents away from the anastomosis, thereby protecting it during the critical postoperative period. [7] Patients who undergo ileostomy face a range of physical and psychological challenges, including altered body image, changes in daily routine, and disruptions to lifestyle and sexual health. [2] While the procedure is life-saving, the presence of a stoma can significantly diminish a patient's quality of life. [8]

Factors such as age, sex, personality, and socioeconomic status play a crucial role in how well a patient adapts to living with an ileostomy. [9-12] Research has consistently shown that individuals with a stoma report a lower quality of life compared to those who undergo similar procedures without stoma formation. [13-15] The

timing of ileostomy closure has been a subject of considerable debate within the medical community. While the reversal procedure is generally considered safe, with recorded mortality rates as low as 0.4%, [16-18] complications such as anastomotic leaks, wound infections, and delayed healing can pose significant risks. A retrospective analysis of 964 ileostomy patients identified several factors that contribute to the failure or delay of stoma closure, including advanced age, concomitant health conditions, and complications from the initial surgery. [19] These findings highlight the complexity of managing ileostomy patients and the need for further research to determine the most effective strategies for improving patient outcomes. This research aims to address the ongoing debate regarding the optimal timing for ileostomy closure by comparing the morbidity and mortality associated with early versus delayed closure. By analyzing the outcomes of patients who undergo early closure (4-6 weeks post-surgery) versus those who have delayed closure (8-12 weeks post-surgery), this study seeks to provide evidence-based recommendations that can guide clinical practice and improve the management of ileostomy patients, particularly in diverse and resource-limited settings.

Methodology

This study was a prospective observational analysis conducted at the Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital, Jaipur, from September 2022 to March 2024. The study aimed to compare the outcomes of early (4-6 weeks) versus delayed (8-12 weeks) ileostomy closure. A total of 60 patients were included, with 30 patients assigned to each group.

The study population comprised patients who had undergone a temporary ileostomy as part of their surgical treatment. Eligible patients were those admitted for ileostomy closure during the study period and who met the inclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were age between 15 and 75 years, patients in good physical and mental health suitable for surgery within 4 to 6 weeks who had given informed consent for the surgery. Patients were excluded if they had a permanent ileostomy, were uncooperative, immunocompromised, had an active chronic infection or any chronic disease, or had recurrent stoma complications or multiple stomas.

Randomization and Group Allocation: Patients were randomly allocated to either the early closure group or the delayed closure group. Randomization

was conducted using a computerized randomization process, ensuring unbiased group allocation. Both groups were followed up for three months post-surgery, with assessments conducted at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months intervals.

Preoperative Assessment: Before surgery, each patient underwent a detailed preoperative assessment, including routine investigations such as complete blood count (CBC), serum electrolytes, liver function tests (LFT), renal function tests (RFT), and specific investigations like ultrasonography, chest X-ray, and distal loopogram. Mechanical bowel preparation with polyethylene glycol was administered a day before surgery, and all patients received preoperative antibiotics, specifically injectable ceftriaxone, at the time of induction.

Surgical Procedure: The ileostomy closure was performed under standardized surgical protocols. A circular incision was made around the stoma, leaving a 2 mm skin margin. The bowel was mobilized, and circumferential dissection was performed to free the bowel loops from adhesions. An end-to-end bowel anastomosis was conducted using a two-layered closure technique: an inner continuous layer with 3-0 polyglactin suture (Connell) and an outer continuous layer with 3-0 silk suture (Lembert). The bowel was then reduced back into the peritoneal cavity, and the fascial

opening was closed with interrupted 1-PDS sutures. A sterile dressing was applied after skin closure.

Parameters Studied: The study evaluated various preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative parameters to compare the outcomes between the early and delayed ileostomy closure groups:

- **Preoperative Parameters:** History and clinical examination, demographic variables, and the indication for ileostomy creation.
- **Intraoperative Parameters:** The presence of intraoperative adhesions and the duration of the operative time.
- **Postoperative Parameters:** Complications such as skin excoriation, wound infection, wound dehiscence, fecal fistula, anastomotic leakage, and mortality. The duration of hospital stay and any readmissions were also recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Data were collected prospectively and entered into an Excel sheet. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 22.0 for Windows.

The data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation for continuous variables and as frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. The Student's t-test and Chi-square test were used to compare the two groups, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Results

The study included a total of 60 patients, evenly divided into two groups: 30 patients in the early ileostomy closure group and 30 in the delayed closure group. The demographic analysis revealed that the majority of patients in both groups were within the 41-50 years age bracket. The mean age of patients in the early closure group was slightly younger compared to the delayed closure group, but this difference was not statistically significant. Gender distribution showed a male predominance, with 63.33% males in the early closure group and 73.33% in the delayed closure group, indicating no significant gender-based differences between the groups.

The indications for stoma formation varied, with enteric perforation being the most common reason, accounting for 56.67% of cases in the early closure group and 66.67% in the delayed closure group. Other indications included Koch's abdomen, traumatic perforation, defunctioning ileostomy, and appendicular perforation, with no significant variation in distribution between the two groups. Intraoperative findings highlighted that adhesions were significantly more frequent in the delayed closure group, with 36.7% of patients experiencing this complication compared to only 10% in the early closure group ($p = 0.015$). Despite this, the mean operative time for ileostomy closure was nearly identical between the two groups, with both

averaging around 77 minutes, suggesting that the timing of closure did not affect the duration of the surgery itself.

Postoperative complications were more common in the early closure group, with a wound infection rate of 26.67% compared to just 3.3% in the delayed closure group, a difference that was statistically significant ($p = 0.004$). Other complications such as wound dehiscence and enterocutaneous fistula were also observed, though at lower frequencies. The mean hospital stay was marginally shorter in the early closure group (6.98 ± 2.71 days) compared to the delayed group (7.25 ± 2.62 days), although this difference was not statistically significant. However, readmission rates were slightly higher in the delayed closure group at 10%, compared to 3.33% in the early closure group. No reoperations were necessary in either group, and mortality was low, with only one death reported in the delayed closure group, resulting in a 3.33% mortality rate.

These findings suggest that while early ileostomy closure may increase the risk of wound infections, it can reduce intraoperative adhesions and shorten hospital stays. Careful patient selection is crucial to minimize the risk of complications associated with early closure. Overall, this study highlights the potential benefits and challenges of early ileostomy closure compared to the traditional delayed approach.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Patients

Characteristic	Early Closure Group (n=30)	Delayed Closure Group (n=30)	p-value
Age Group (years)			
15-20	7 (23.33%)	9 (30%)	0.69
21-30	6 (20%)	7 (23.33%)	
31-40	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	
41-50	8 (26.67%)	8 (26.67%)	
>50	5 (16.67%)	4 (13.33%)	
Gender			
Male	19 (63.33%)	22 (73.33%)	0.17
Female	11 (36.67%)	8 (26.67%)	
Indications			
Enteric perforation	17 (56.67%)	20 (66.67%)	0.54
Koch's abdomen	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	
Traumatic perforation	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	
Defunctioning ileostomy	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	
Appendicular perforation	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	
Intraoperative Adhesions			
Yes	3 (10%)	11 (36.7%)	0.015 (S)
No	27 (90%)	19 (63.3%)	
Post-stoma closure complications			
None	19 (63.33%)	27 (90%)	0.004 (S)
Wound Infection	8 (26.67%)	1 (3.3%)	
Wound Dehiscence	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.3%)	
Anastomotic Leak	0 (0%)	1 (3.3%)	
Hospital Stay (days)	6.98 ± 2.71	7.25 ± 2.62	0.77
Readmission	1 (3.33%)	3 (10%)	0.29

Discussion

The current prospective observational study was conducted from September 2022 to March 2024 in the surgical department of Mahatma Gandhi Medical College & Hospital in Jaipur. Sixty individuals were admitted for ileostomy closure up until March 2024. Thirty of these patients had early ileostomy closure, while the remaining thirty had delayed ileostomy closure. The study's primary objective was to compare the morbidity and mortality incidence between early (4 to 6 weeks) and delayed (8 to 12 weeks) ileostomy closure. In both cohorts, there were significantly more men than women. The gender distribution within the study groups was similar. The largest group of individuals was aged 41–50 years, followed by those aged 15–20 years. The age range with the fewest subjects was 31–40 years. There was no discernible difference in age distribution between the groups. Enteric perforation was the most frequent indication of stoma formation among the study participants. Six participants reported Koch's abdomen, traumatic perforation, and defunctioning ileostomy.

There was a statistically significant difference in the number of reported complications related to stoma formation between the delayed and early ileostomy groups. In this study, 13.3% and 3.3% of participants in the early group had skin excoriation and prolapse, respectively, compared to 30% and 13.3% in the delayed group. Similar results were reported by Sarawgi M et al. [20], who found that intestinal perforation was the most frequent cause of stoma formation in 62% of cases. This contrasts sharply with the Western world, where the majority of significant anastomotic leaks—associated with high morbidity and mortality rates—are treated with a temporary covering ileostomy, particularly in low rectal anastomoses. In the early closure group, only 4 patients suffered skin excoriation, compared to 9 patients in the late closure group preoperatively. Four patients in the late closure group had prolapsed stomas, but only one in the early group. Garcia-Botello et al. [21] found that 39.4% of patients experienced ileostomy-related issues, with skin-related conditions such as erythema (7.1%) and dermatitis (12.6%) being the most frequent. In a different study, 63.33% of patients had difficulties linked to their ileostomy, which was performed for an intestinal perforation. The most frequent side effect was peristomal skin excoriation, followed by retraction (13.33%), weight loss (13.33%), electrolyte imbalance (10%), and prolapse (3.33%). The lack of appropriate stoma care services in India motivated our consideration of early stoma closure as a means of reducing stoma-related complications.

None of the subjects required reoperation. Although there was no discernible difference,

readmission was more frequently recorded in the delayed (10%) ileostomy group than in the early (3.33%) group. The mean hospital stay was 6.98 ± 2.71 days for the early group and 7.25 ± 2.62 days for the delayed group. Although not statistically significant, the mean hospital stay was slightly higher in the delayed group. Abdalla S et al. [22] also found that early ileostomy closure can significantly reduce the average number of postoperative complications and hospital stay duration. Alves A et al. [23] conducted a prospective randomized experiment, dividing 186 patients into two groups who underwent either early closure of a loop ileostomy (within 8 days) or late closure (at 60 days). The early group reported a significantly shorter length of stay than the late group (16 vs. 18 days, respectively; $P = .013$). Similarly, Omundsen M et al. [24] found that early ileostomy closure resulted in a significantly shorter hospital stay (14 vs. 17 days, respectively; $P = .05$). With a statistically significant difference of $p < 0.05$, post-stoma closure complications were observed more frequently in the early ileostomy groups compared to the delayed groups. Wound infection was the most frequent post-stoma closure complication, followed by wound dehiscence. In this study, one patient in the delayed ileostomy group passed away, compared to no mortality observed in the early ileostomy group.

Minor complications are defined as anastomosis-related problems that arise after the stoma has closed and do not necessitate repeat surgery. These mild problems, such as ileus, sepsis, and abscess, have been documented in the literature, with a patient complication range of 4-5% to 30%. 84 Similar results were observed in the study by Sarawgi M et al. [20], who did not identify any anastomotic leaks, intra-abdominal abscesses, or mortality rates in the early closure group. Nadim K et al. [25] found a 5.76% leak rate and a 1.2% mortality rate in their assessment of early closure of temporary loop stomas. The literature implies an anastomotic leak rate of 0% to 8% after ileostomy closure, depending on the timing. Our study focused on temporary loop ileostomies, and in terms of anastomotic leak and death rates, our outcomes are comparable to or even better than prior studies on both early and delayed stoma closures. Even when performed earlier, stoma closure can be successfully achieved with strict adherence to surgical principles, thorough tissue mobilization, and cautious patient selection. [20]

Conclusion

This study provides a comparative analysis of early versus delayed ileostomy closure, focusing on key clinical outcomes such as postoperative complications, intraoperative findings, and overall patient recovery. The results indicate that while early ileostomy closure is associated with a higher

incidence of wound infections, it significantly reduces the risk of intraoperative adhesions and shortens the duration of hospital stay. The absence of significant differences in mortality rates and the lack of need for reoperations suggest that early closure is a feasible and safe alternative for select patients. However, the decision to pursue early closure must be made with careful consideration of the patient's overall health status, the potential for complications, and the specific clinical context. While early closure can expedite recovery and improve the quality of life by reducing the time patients live with a stoma, it requires meticulous surgical technique and close postoperative monitoring to mitigate the risk of complications. In conclusion, early ileostomy closure presents a viable option that can be beneficial for many patients, particularly when balanced against the risks and challenges associated with prolonged stoma maintenance. Further research is recommended to refine patient selection criteria and to explore the long-term outcomes of both early and delayed closure strategies, thereby optimizing surgical practices and patient care in ileostomy management.

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